

A review study of Shadangapaniya in *Jwara chikitsa* with special reference to fever

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 567–572

Publication history: Received on 11 December 2022; revised on 18 January 2023; accepted on 21 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0112>

Abstract

In today's era, diseases are increasing rapidly and medical facilities are becoming expensive. In such a situation, diseases can be avoided through *Ayurvedic* remedies and at the same time, cheap treatment of many diseases is also available in *Ayurveda*. Fever is a minor disease but sometimes it takes terrible form. Allopathic has a lot of side effects of antibiotics and anti-pyretic due to which, in diseases like fever, *Ayurveda* should be preferred. *Sadang-paniya* is herbal medicine which is beneficial in fever as well as is very effective in burning, extreme thirst, fatigue. Fever is called *Jwarain Ayurveda* and *Jwarais* described in *Ayurveda* as a separate disease. In this article, along with *Ayurvedic* view of *Jwara*, *Sadang-paniya* will study in detail.

Keywords: Fever; *Jwara*; *Sadand-paniya*; Anti-pyretic

1. Introduction

Through *Ayurveda*, we get to know not only medical knowledge but also ways of living life. *Ayurveda* not only helps to maintain health but also cures the disease. At the time of birth and death fever is present. In *Ayurveda* fever is *Jwara*, which is considering an important disease as it afflicts the body, mind and senses. In *Ayurveda*, *Jwara* has been described with its etiology, sign symptoms and managing principle.^[1,2] Many treatments for fever have been described. As *Agni Dushti* is the main cause in the manifestation of *Jwara*. Along with medication, routine and food also contribute to the treatment of *Jwara*. According to *Ayurveda*, *Jwara* is caused due by the weakness of *Jatharagni* and the formation of *Ama*. In *Ayurveda*, many diet Plans and medicines have been described as per the condition of *Jwaraa*. *Shadangapaniya* is a medicated water that is made by six medicinal herbs i.e. *Musta*, *Parpatak*, *Usheera*, *Chandana*, *Uddichya*, *Nagar*. It is useful in *Jwara*, *Pipasa* (Thrust), *Kshram* (weariness). All these diseases are very annoying and due to *Ama dosha* and *PittaDosha*. There is a lot of cost in the treatment of these diseases and treatment is also difficult. But *Ayurveda* gives very simple and easy treatment for all these diseases, which saves money.

Aim

To get a more clear vision on the effect of *Shadangapaniyain* all types of *Jwara*.

Objective

To study *Shadangapaniya* as the adjuvant medicated liquid useful in all kinds of *Jwara*

2. Material and methods

Conceptual Study Materials are *Ayurvedic* books, *Ayurveda* text, journals, the internet & advice from the learned experts.

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2.1. Observations

Ayurveda considers the origin of *Jwara* is from lord *Shiva*. *Jwara* is considered as supreme among all the diseases named by a different name in the different creature,^[3,4] *Jwara* is a disease and a symptom in other diseases.

2.1.1. Nidana (Causative factor)

The *Strotas* involved in the occurrence of *Jwara* are *Rasavaha* and *Swedavaha*. *Nidana*, *samprapti* and *lakshanas* have been described separately for *vataj*, *pittaja*, *kaphaja*, *Dwandaja*, *sannipataja Jwaraa*.^[5] *Guru Ahara* and *Pragyapradh* are also causing of *Jwara*. The common causative factor for all kinds of *Jwaraa* has been described in *Ayurveda* i.e. *Snehadi karmamithyayoga* (improper application of *oleation*, *sudation*), *Abhighaat*(*Trauma*), *Rogothana prapakata* (at the occurrence of disease), *Sharma* (fatigue), *Kshaya* (wasting of body tissues), (ingestion of unwholesome food), *rutu viparyaya*(not following the seasonal regimen), *oushadhi pushpa gandha* (inhale the medicated flowers), *shoka*(grief), *nakshatrapeeda*(the curse of stars), *abhichar* (improper social behavior), *abhishap* (curse from other people), *manasikaabhishang* (psychological disturbances), *Apprajata*(not having normal labor), *ahita sevan prajata* (not following the postnatal care), *stanyaavataran* (lactation).^[6]

2.1.2. Purvarupa (Prodromal sign)

Aalasya, *nayanarava*, *jrumbha*, *klama*, *bhakta dwesha*, *gourava*, *avipaka*, *aasyavairasya*, *balahani*, *varnahani*, *alpa sheela vaikruta* are *purvaroop* of *Jwaraa*.^[7] *Jambha in Vataj Jwara*, *Nayan Daha* (burning sensation in eyes) in *Pittaja Jwara*, and no desire for food in *Kaphaja Jwara* are a specific prodromal signs.

2.1.3. Samprapti

The vitiated *Doshas* when pulls out the *Aamaashaya ushma* into *Rasavaha* and *Swedavaha Strotas*. The obstruction occurs in a *Strotas*, *Agni* get diminished, and manifest the *Jwara*.

2.1.4. Samanya Jwaraa Chikitsa

The principles of *Jwaraa chikitsa* have been described in *Ayurveda* which is *Laghu Apartapan*, *Kashayapaan*, *Abhyanga*, *Sneha*, *Sweda*, *Pradeha*, *Parisheka*, *Lepana*, *Vaman*, *Virechana*, *Aasthapana*, *Anuvasan*, *Nasya*, *Dhupa*, *Dhuma* and *Sarpi Pana* in *Chronic fever*.^[18,19]

2.1.5. Shadangapaniya

The *Shadangapaniya* prepared with six medicinal herbs viz., *Musta*,^[10] *Parpatak*,^[11] *Usheera*,^[12] *Chandana*,^[13] *Uddichya*,^[14] *Nagar*.^[15] *Rasapanchaka* and *Doshagnata* are described in table no 1

Table 1 *Rasapanchaka* of *Shadangapaniya*

Herb	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	Prabhava	Doshaghnta
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Tikta, katu kashaya</i>	<i>Ruksha Laghu</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Grahi, Dipana, Pachana, Lekhan</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta Hara</i>
<i>Parpatak</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha Tikshana</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta Hara</i>
<i>Usheera</i>	<i>Tikta, Madhur</i>	<i>Ruksha Laghu</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pachana, Stambhana</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta Hara</i>
<i>Chandan</i>	<i>Tikta, Madhur</i>	<i>Ruksha Laghu</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Varnya, Dahaprashaman</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta Hara</i>
<i>Udichya</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Ruksha Laghu</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Deepan, pachan, hrallas</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta Hara</i>
<i>Nagar</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha Tikshana</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Deepana, Bhedan</i>	<i>Vata-Kapha Hara</i>

The overall analysis of the drugs among *Shadangapaniya* is as follows.

2.2. Rasa

Among the six drugs the predominant *rasa* is *tikta* (bitter), then *madhura* (sweet) and followed by *katu* (pungent) and *kashay* (astringent). *Tikta rasa* is superior to mitigate the *Jwara*, *Pipasa* as it does the *aamapachana*, *aamashayakleda nashaka*, *agni deepaka*. *Shadanga paneeya* is having dominancy of *tikta rasa*, therefore useful to counteract the *samprapti* of *Jwaraa*. As per *Doshaja* predominance, *tikta* mitigate the *pitta dosha*, *Kashaya* mitigates the *kapha dosha* and *madhura* mitigate the *vata dosha*. Therefore on analysis of *rasa* combination of *shadanga paneeya*, it is useful in all kinds of *Jwaraa*.

2.3. Guna (Properties)

Among the six drugs, the predominant *guna* is *laghu*, *ruksha*, followed by *guru* and *teekshna*. *Laghu* and *Ruksha guna* having the predominance of *vayu*, *aakasha* and *agni mahabhutas*. These properties are useful in the depletion of *aama*. Due to these properties, it is useful in *santarpanottha Jwara*.

Guru property is useful in nourishment as it is having *prithvi* and *aapa mahabhuta* predominance. Due to this *guna* it is useful in *kshataj*, *kshajay* and *vataj Jwara*. *Teekshna guna* by its nature works rapidly in the body.

Therefore the combination of these properties in *Shadangapaniya* is applicable in all kinds of *Jwara*.

2.4. Veerya (Active Principle)

The predominance of *sheeta veerya* is present among the drugs of *Shadangapaniya* along with the lesser proportion of *ushna veerya*. *Jwarais* a disease of *ushna* in nature therefore *sheeta veerya* drugs are useful in it. Also in conditions like *sheetapurvak Jwara* (fever with chills) *Shadangapaniya* is useful as it contain *ushna veerya* drug also. *Shadangapaniyais* useful in *vishaja Jwara* due to *Sheet virya*.

2.5. Vipaka

Sadangapaniya having *Katu* and *madhura vipaka* with dominancy of *katu vipaka*. As *katu vipaka* does the *aamapachana*, *aamashayakleda nashaka* which is useful in all types of *Jwara*. *Madhura vipaka* is useful in *vataj*, *bhayaja*, and *shokaj Jwara*. Therefore the *vipaka* of *shadanga paneeya* is present in such a way that it is useful in all types of *Jwara*.

2.6. Karma (Pharmacological action)

So here the combination involved in *Shadangapaniya* is effective in dengue, typhoid and exhibiting antimalarial effect. These drugs are also exhibiting the antimicrobial effect by which they are useful in pyrexia caused by the infections of those microbes. Advance researches have also revealed the antipyretic effect of these drugs.

Table 2 Dravya karmukatva (Mode of action of herbs)

Herb	Pharmacological action
<i>Musta</i>	Trishna Nigrahana
<i>Parpatak</i>	Dah Prashaman
<i>Usheera</i>	Aamapachana
<i>Chandan</i>	Pachana with Pittashaman
<i>Udichya</i>	Dah Prashaman
<i>Nagar</i>	Aamapachana, Agnideepana

2.7. Musta (Cyperus rotundus Linn.)^[16]

The *cyperus rotundus* tubers from that the isolation of patchoulene, caryophyllene or-oxide, 10, 12-peroxycalamene and 4, 7-dimethyl-1-tetralone has been done. These compounds had shown antiprotozoal activities because of the higher effectualness at EC₅₀ 2.33 × 10⁻⁶ M. The Cyperaceae oil had shown the antibacterial activity among varied microorganisms. The microorganisms viz., *klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus Vulgaris*, true bacteria *pyogenes*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, *S.Aureus* were studied by victimization inhibition zone methodology (Aromatogram). The MIC and MBC for every microorganism were calculable. The oil of *cyperus rotundus* was shown associate degree

effectualness over the bacterium, during which effectualness was a lot of among the Gram-positive bacterium, as compared to the gram-negative bacterium. The bacterium results in infection within the body. Any infection within the body results in fever, as *musta* has shown medicinal drug activity for varied microorganisms the drug is beneficial for fever.

2.8. Parpataka (*Fumaria parviflora* Lam.)^[17]

Fumaria indica (parviflora) possesses 2 major phytochemicals Narlum icine and Oxysanguinarine, these 2 area units efficacious within the inhibition of breakbone fever virus (DENV). The binding affinity is over eight kcal/mol against DENV4- NS4B. These phytochemicals area unit extremely reactive within the binding the pocket of DENV4- NS4B, supported ELUMO, EHOMO and band energy gap.

2.9. Usheera (*Vetiveria zizanoides* (Linn.) Nash.)^[18]

Extract of *Vetiveria zizanoides* at seventy-five mg, 150mg and three hundred mg/ weight unit dose had shown the many reductions within the elevated temperature that was occurred thanks to the shot of yeast suspension (10ml/kg body weight).

The oil of the *santalum album* had shown an actual antibacterial effect against penicillin-resistant staphylococci aurous and antifungal resistant fungus species. The oil additionally exhibits the inhibition against Herpes simplex virus sort one. The santol has shown the anti-influenza activity against the H3N2 virus. wood spirit extract of tree effective against *Bacillus subtilis*, *typhoid bacillus*, *staphylococci aureus* and genus *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and extremely active against *Candida albicans*.

2.10. Uddichya (*Pavonia odorata* Willd.)

Pavonia odorata has shown a nice anti- microorganism activity against *S.aureus*, bacterium respiratory illness, *Chrysoporium Indicum* and *Botrydiplodia sps*.

2.11. Nagar (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.)^[20]

An ethanolic extract of Canton ginger was shown the medicament, analgesic, antipyretic, antimicrobial and hypoglycemic activities. In rats, the extract of Canton ginger had shown the reduction within the carrageenan-induced paw swelling and yeast-evoked fever. The *zingiber officinale* had shown the effectualness within the inhibition of the expansion of each Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterium.

3. Discussion

Jwara is described in Ayurveda separately. *Rasawaha* and *Swedavaha Strotas* involve in the Samprapti of *Jwara*. The *Jwara* is originated from the stomach. Aam is the main cause of *Jwara*. The treatment principle as per prodromal signs, *aamavastha* has been described. *its* administration of specific medicine as per the *dosha* involvement in the prodromal stage has been described viz., *vataj- pure ghee, pittaj- virechana, kaphaja – mru du prachachardhana*.

The paneeya has been mentioned in Charaka samhita in *Jwara* as, as *Ushna jala* in *vata kapha Jwara*, *Tiktaka shruta sheeta jala* in *madyaja* and *paittika Jwara*, *Shadangapaniya* in all kinds of *Jwara*. *Shadanga* contains six drugs, viz., *musta, parpatak, usheera, chandana, uddichya, nagar*. The conceptual analysis of *Shadangapaniya* in context with their Rasa, Guna, Veerya, Vipaka, *Karma* highlights the applicability in all kinds of *Jwara*.

Shadanga contains six drugs, viz., *musta, parpatak, usheera, chandana, uddichya, nagar*. Every drug had shown the antimicrobial effect in a different spectrum. The microorganisms are responsible for the infection which in turn induces the fever. Hence the inhibition of the microorganism will control the infection and help in the reduction of fever.

The *Cyperus rotundus* was shown efficacy over the Gram-positive bacteria and Gram-negative bacteria. *Parpataka* is efficacious in the inhibition of the dengue virus (DENV). *Usheera* is efficacious in fever due to yeast. *Uddichhya* is effective against *S.aureus*, *Diplococcus pneumonia*, *Chrysoporium Indicum* and *Botrydiplodia sps*. The *Santalum album* is effective against Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus and antimitotic resistant *Candida* species Herpes simplex virus Type 1e, H3N2 virus, *Bacillus subtiles*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida albicans*. *Zingiber officinale* had shown the reduction in yeast-induced fever and show the inhibition of the growth of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Shown in researches the antipyretic effect ranging from dengue, malaria, typhoid to an exhibition of antimicrobial effect.

4. Conclusion

Shadanga paneeya is a unique combination of different herbs, which under its combination of *different Rasa, Guna, Veerya, Vipaka* useful in all kinds of *Jwara*. The combination possesses the antipyretic effect in all kinds of fever which are originating from the viral, bacterial and parasitic origin. Therefore this is to conclude that *shadanga paniya* as the adjuvant medicated liquid is useful in all kinds of *Jwara*.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I express gratitude to the Department of Kayachikitsa and Hospital Authority for giving me this opportunity to study this particular research topic. Special thanks to Secretary of Maharashtra Arogya Mandal's Secretary, Hon'ble Mr. Anil Gujar, Hon'ble Principal Dr. Nilesh Phule and Faculty members Dr.Yogesh Kotangle, Dr. Vijayalaxmi Patil, Dr. Ritesh Damle, Dr. Kiran Ubhe for co-operating throughout the research study. Many thanks to Dr. Arjun Sable and to my colleagues, as we got to learn many new things while reviewing the research articles and our knowledge regarding the subject has been increased.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of manuscript.

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